

ASSESSMENT OF THE TEACHING EFFECTIVENESS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION SUBJECT TEACHERS FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF CONTENT DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of teaching Physical Education subject teachers from the perspective of content development. The main focus of the study is to identify teachers' tendencies in presenting information, developing students' skills, and providing feedback in the learning process. The research method used is a survey with a quantitative descriptive approach. The population in this study were Physical Education teachers in Medan, North Sumatra, with a sample of 76 teachers. Data collection techniques were carried out through observation using previously validated instruments. Observations were made by analyzing 30-minute learning videos to assess the frequency of providing information, skill extension, skill refinement, and skill application in teaching. The results showed that the majority of teachers provided more information (73.68%) and basic skill application (67.11%) compared to further skill development (14.47%) and skill refinement (22.37%). This shows a tendency for learning that is still centered on the teacher, with the main focus on delivering material rather than developing students' skills gradually. In conclusion, the effectiveness of Physical Education teachers' teaching can still be improved by emphasizing more progressive skill development and providing more optimal feedback. A more adaptive learning strategy is needed so that students not only understand basic movements, but are also able to develop and hone their skills in more depth.

Keywords: Teaching Effectiveness, Physical Education, Content Development, Learning Strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching as facilitating the learning experience of students. All physical education programs focus on what they want to teach their students ¹. Learning experience is defined as a set of instructional conditions and learning events that restructure the learner's experience and are related to the learning objectives. Physical education teachers must always remember that learning objectives are the key words here. In other words, learning experiences lead to a goal, so they imply a journey from a place.

This condition is where the central concept of effective teaching lies, namely in the learning objectives. In general, effective teaching is the practice of physical education teachers in facilitating meaningful learning experiences for learners and which result in desired outcomes². In addition, the educational value and contribution of the spectrum to students can only be

achieved if various teaching and learning styles are used appropriately ³. Effective teaching requires a variety of strategies, techniques and approaches to engage learners, develop their understanding and skills, and support their overall growth and development.

The quality and status of the physical education teaching profession depends on competent, effective and efficient teachers, and effective teaching produces well-trained and skilled learners ⁴. A strategy consists of a set of carefully selected teaching skills and teaching elements. Only through the design and use of these basic components can a strategy successfully produce the desired learning outcomes ⁵.

Based on postulate theory, empirical studies show that motor skill competence is an enabling factor that provides the physical foundation necessary for enjoyable and successful physical activity (PA) engagement in adolescents ⁶. Beginning physical education teachers need to understand the meaning of professionalism, professionals must be prepared early in their careers to provide best practices ⁷. The orientation of physical education values adopted by teachers tends to be dominated by child-centered values. Among the child-centered values, the most dominant value is the effort to actualize the potential of students. While the most dominant value of mastering material is the instillation of sports values in students ⁸.

Teaching is a difficult task. Learning for students is its aim. The teaching-learning process must be guided mostly by the teacher. This is why it might be challenging to teach. The teacher needs to figure out how to effectively reach a kid who isn't learning. Teachers will wish to teach a variety of skills, knowledge, and values to a wide range of students ⁷. Many students feel anxious about communication (speaking) during meetings, especially because of diction, tone of voice, shyness, and fear of failure in front of their peers and teachers. This shows that their peers are afraid of failing in class. ⁹.

Most prospective physical education teachers prefer the more traditional game and sports curriculum model with a custodial orientation, which they themselves experienced as children. If each new generation of teachers imitates their own experience with physical education, they tend to learn from the experience "on the receiving end" that the meaning and purpose of physical education (what the subject is about) is usually found in sports and, in particular, in team games. As a result, when many teachers arrive at the training stage, they have become accustomed to associating physical education primarily with "school sports" ¹⁰. The practice of reasoning and making sense are two reasons to believe that the distinction is theoretically based if a teacher wants to improve his or her understanding of learning concepts ¹¹.

In the context of physical education, there are many aspects that determine whether a teaching can be said to be effective or not. Some examples of these aspects are (1) clear learning objectives, (2) active involvement of students, (3) differentiated teaching, (4) progression and phasing or development of content, (5) demonstration of skills and explanations, (6) feedback, (7) effective communication, (8) assessment and evaluation, and (9) safety ¹². Family influences do not appear to be significant in terms of students' physical activity at school. As well as sports skills, students' participation in sports activities, tendency to engage in spontaneous physical activity, or gender, this study underlines the importance of the school

environment in supporting children's physical activity, which is especially important for children from disadvantaged families or backgrounds, confirming the hypothesis that school transition affects physical activity and that environmental conditions are significant determinants of physical activity levels ¹³.

Teaching and learning are complex phenomena, and researchers have found that teacher efficacy plays a significant role. Teachers' sense of efficacy appears to influence basic beliefs about students and instruction and their choice of teaching methods, as well as students' beliefs about their own abilities and learning ¹⁴.

One of the important pedagogical competencies is how teachers break down content and sequence it into appropriate learning experiences for students. For this, teachers use task programming in order to guide students' journey from beginner to advanced level. Together, the four teacher moves describing the type of task constitute the progression through which the teacher develops the content. 1) Informing. The initial task in the progression of a skill. 2) Extension. A teacher move that communicates a concern for changing the complexity or difficulty of student performance. 3) Refinement. A teacher move that communicates a concern for the quality of student performance. 4) Application/Assessment. A teacher move that communicates a concern for moving the student focus from how to do the movement to how to use the movement or an assessment of form ⁷. The involvement of universities in research with schools and teachers is basically related to curriculum and pedagogical development in schools. This is a professional development of teachers that cannot be separated from the role of universities ¹⁵. Effective learning certainly requires supporting facilities and environmental conditions. Physical education learning emphasizes movement skills, which will help achieve overall educational goals. In the context of the educational environment, efforts to provide teaching methods with various media as facilities and supporters are normal ¹⁶.

This study will discuss only the parts that are considered important for the current context and situation. Physical education teachers, at least, will get help in assessing their teaching process through the presentation of movement tasks, progression, and phasing (content development). Physical education teachers will return to physical education as an adventure. The journey requires preparation, as do other things in our lives. In this case, the role of physical education teachers is very important because they are responsible for creating movement-based sports lessons.

METHOD

The research method used is the survey research method. The survey method is used to obtain data from certain natural places, but researchers carry out treatment in data collection, for example by distributing questionnaires, structured interview tests and so on ¹⁷ This research is included in the type of descriptive research with a quantitative approach, descriptive research is "research that really only describes what exists and happens in a certain place, field or area, the collected data is clarified and grouped according to type, nature or condition then conclusions are drawn ¹⁸. The population and sample in this study were 76 Physical Education Teachers in Medan, Sumatra Utara. The data collection technique in this study was carried out

using observation to determine the level of results obtained in each variable. The observation instrument to be used has been validated and then tested on 30 Physical Education Teachers. The instrument was analyzed by researchers using content validity. Methods for calculating the tasks required to edit texts and content transcription for each category. Thus, the final report is made by collecting selected texts in coding from the appropriate files, along with documentation to support evidence ¹⁹. The data analysis technique in this study uses quantitative descriptive techniques. Descriptive analysis is used in presenting data, then the data is analyzed quantitatively, then the processed data is presented in the form of a percentage.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

A teacher in content development will show several characteristics in his/her pedagogy, namely:

- a) Determining the stage of progress. We all know that teachers increase the learning experience from simple to complex or easy to difficult through various task extensions. Starting with the easy or simple, the teacher then adds difficulty and complexity.
- b) Focus on performance quality (refinement). Teachers who are effective in developing content are characterized by their teaching that pays attention to the quality of their students' movement performance. If teachers desire this quality, their attention will be demonstrated by providing feedback to students on how they perform certain skills. Future research will specifically address feedback.
- c) Providing opportunities to apply/assess skills (Application). There is a simple formula in meaningful learning, namely direct application. Students will learn a lot by practicing skills in physical education. But how these skills are applied in the context of real movement is often not a concern. When teachers give students the opportunity to apply the skills they have learned is an important characteristic in content development. Especially when this application is carried out after the task for refining the movement is done. Application can be done by providing modified sports games or through self-tests. It should be underlined together here that this application can take place in the continuum of teacher teaching. This means that teachers can provide application tasks throughout the time they learn a skill or at the end when the skill has been mastered. For example, after learning some futsal techniques and skills, students are given the opportunity to play in a modified or real game. As a competitive game, futsal aims to score goals (effectiveness) not how to move to score goals (efficiency).

To conduct content analysis observations, videos of learning activities of physical education teachers in the field were viewed for 30 minutes. After the assessment results were collected, data and values from each variable of the physical education learning content analysis were collected. The results will be grouped based on the category and percentage of each variable of the physical education learning content analysis.

The data results from each of these variables are as follows:

1) Information: Initial task in the progression of a skill.

The level of teacher tendency to provide information is more dominant in the high category (73.68%), namely 56 teachers who provide information above 7 times, second in the medium category (19.74%), namely 15 teachers who provide information between 5 - 7 times and only 5 people (6.58%) are in the low category, namely 5 teachers who provide information less than 5 times. So overall it can be concluded that the provision of information by physical education teachers during teaching practice still tends to provide a lot of information to students. This is an indication that is very ineffective and tends to make learning centered on the teacher. The percentage of indicators for this information variable is presented in table 1 as follows:

Table 1: Provision of Information

No	Category	Number of Teachers	Percentage
1	High Information (≥ 8 x)	56	73,68%
2	Medium Information (5 - 7 x)	15	19,74%
3	Low Information (≤ 4 x)	5	6,58%
Amount		76	100%

2) Extension: Gradual progress in difficulty or complexity.

Teachers change the complexity or difficulty of student performance. Included in this extension is when teachers have to reduce the difficulty or complexity of the movement for any reason. The tendency of teachers to provide extensions is more dominant in the low category (78.95%), namely 60 teachers who provide extensions less than 5 times, second in the medium category (6.58%), namely 5 teachers who provide information between 5 - 7 times and as many as 14.47% who are in the high category, namely 11 teachers who provide extensions more than 7 times. So overall it can be concluded that the provision of extensions carried out by physical education teachers during teaching practices still tends to provide less extensions to students. This is an indication that is very ineffective and tends to pay less attention to the principle of difference and is centered on students. The percentage of indicators for this information variable is presented in table 2 as follows:

Table 2: Granting Extensions

No	Category	Number of Teachers	Percentage
1	High Extensions (≥ 8 x)	11	14,47%
2	Medium Extensions (5 - 7 x)	5	6,58%
3	Low Extensions (≤ 4 x)	60	78,95%
Amount		76	100%

3) Refinement: Teachers' attention to the quality of students' performance.

Usually, this is done by providing feedback to them. The level of teacher tendency to provide refinement is more dominant in the low category (64.47%), namely 49 teachers who provide refinement less than 5 times, second in the medium category (13.16%), namely 10 teachers

who provide information between 5 - 7 times and as many as 22.37% are in the high category, namely 17 teachers who provide refinement more than 7 times. So overall it can be concluded that the provision of refinement carried out by physical education teachers during teaching practice still tends to provide less refinement to students. This is an indication that is very ineffective and tends to pay less attention to the principle of difference and is centered on students. The percentage of indicators for this information variable is presented in table 3 as follows:

Table 3: Refinement Grant

No	Category	Number of Teachers	Percentage
1	High Refinement (≥ 8 x)	17	22,37%
2	Medium Refinement (5 - 7 x)	10	13,16%
3	Low Refinement (≤ 4 x)	49	64,47%
Amount		76	76

4) Implementation: Experience in applying learned skills.

Here the teacher will shift his/her pedagogical focus from how to perform the movement to how to use/assess the movement. The level of teacher tendency to provide implementation is more dominant in the high category (67.11%), namely 51 teachers who provide implementation more than 7 times, second in the medium category (21.05%), namely 16 teachers who provide implementation between 5 - 7 times and only 9 people (11.84%) are in the low category, namely 5 teachers who provide implementation less than 5 times. So overall it can be concluded that the provision of information by physical education teachers during teaching practice still tends to provide a lot of implementation to students. This is an indication that is very ineffective and tends to make learning too fast in providing application experience to students. The percentage of indicators for this application variable is presented in table 4 as follows:

Table 4: Implementation Grant

No	Category	Number of Teachers	Percentage
1	High Implementation (≥ 8 x)	51	67,11%
2	Medium Implementation (5 - 7 x)	16	21,05%
3	Low Implementation (≤ 4 x)	9	11,84%
Amount		76	100%

One of the most important tasks of a physical education teacher is to develop content in a way that will enable children to learn and benefit from the activity. The results of this study reinforce the definition of four functions that teachers might use in developing content. The first function is to inform, or present information to children—ideally in short instructional episodes accompanied by demonstration and/or pointing. Once the initial task is presented, the teacher's next function is to decide whether to make the task easier or more difficult. The success rate (ideally 80 percent) is one measure used in making this decision. The third function in content development is to provide cues to children that increase their understanding and efficiency in performing a particular skill or activity. Teachers should provide only one cue at a time and ensure that the feedback they provide is congruent (approximately the cue). The final teacher

function is to challenge children to maintain their interest in a task, rather than moving on to a more difficult task. Teachers can use two techniques to adapt lessons to individual differences. In invitational teaching, the teacher lets the children make decisions, whereas in intratask variation, the teacher decides which tasks are most appropriate for children with different skill levels²⁰. Effective teacher practice opportunities provide children with many opportunities to practice. One way to indirectly assess the amount of practice opportunities students receive in the classroom is to have a student assistant observe and record the amount of practice for a given student. The focus is on learning concepts, principles, and self-management skills that provide the foundation for becoming knowledgeable consumers who are able to make good decisions in the future²¹. The teacher may wish to select children to observe, or the learning assistant may select two or more children to observe.

This technique is most successful when the lesson focuses on a discrete skill such as rolling, catching, or kicking that can be written down on a form before the lesson. In line with Gabriel Barros da Cunha, physical education teachers tend to use the Traditional Learning Model (TEM) which emphasizes teaching sports techniques individually, through analytical methods and in a contextualized learning environment of play, model-based learning emphasizes learning tasks that take into account the chaotic and unpredictable nature of collective sports play²². The results of the study assume that in the assessment of the performance of physical education teachers, of the four competencies, the most dominant are personal and social competencies compared to pedagogical and professional competencies. This reinforces that teachers still tend to act traditionally in their teaching practices.²³

The life journey of teachers enters the classroom with direction provided by some combination of personal knowledge of subject matter, content standards, and instructional materials. As teachers gain experience, they are expected to develop a better understanding of how the journey ahead will unfold in terms of timing, progress milestones, and specific routes, with full attention to the needs and interests of their learners. Each year, learners affirm to these teachers that the journey is a shared endeavor and that the best-laid plans of the best teachers are just that, plans, subject to change²⁴. Teachers and students interact to determine the nature of the work that students do. More specifically, teachers influence what students learn by explaining the specifications of tasks, providing explanations of the processes that can be used to complete the work, acting as a resource as students work, and managing accountability for the product. An important element of instruction is how teachers determine and structure the work that students must do²⁵. Teachers must not only challenge students' beliefs about what it means to teach, but they must also challenge their own views about teacher education²⁶.

The same thing was also conveyed in the results of Tri Ani Hastuti research, namely that good teachers can provide affection and attention to students, have the desire to develop their knowledge of the subjects they teach, and provide support and encouragement in helping students achieve their best. Pedagogical competence develops as a scientific tool and method that bridges the gap in achievement and intrinsic quality as a result of social and economic disparities and improves personal quality and learning achievement²⁷. In the context of physical education, it is often found that teachers tend to focus more on providing information

and applying basic skills compared to extension (further skill development) and skill refinement. Some of the reasons why this happens include: 1). Time constraints: Teachers often feel that there is not enough learning time to move on to the skill refinement stage, so they focus more on the basics. 2). Focus on quick results: There is a push to ensure that students understand basic movements, while developing higher skills is considered a secondary priority. 3). Teacher perception: Some teachers may feel that students are not ready for the extension or refinement stage, so they prefer to repeat the basics. 4). Outcome-based evaluation: The curriculum or assessment system sometimes places more emphasis on mastering basic skills than on the gradual process of skill development. However, to help learners acquire more complex skills, improve movement quality, and build confidence, extension and refinement stages are essential in motor learning theory. Teachers can try using step-by-step methods, such as 1) graded challenges that move from basic to advanced, 2) specific feedback that tells learners what they did wrong and how to improve, and 3) structured practice that combines basic skills with additional challenges to enhance learner experience. Too much material to teach given the amount of time available is a common problem faced by teachers. In certain areas, such as history and science, where the knowledge base is constantly expanding, this problem becomes even more serious. To overcome this problem of content “overload,” teachers must continually make content choices ²⁴.

Any teacher knows how important student practice is; however, students must remain vigilant when practicing. Appropriate, informed, and focused practice is essential. Teachers can encourage their students to do the same work if they know that their students are capable. This has the potential to increase homework productivity because homework is usually just continued practice outside of class ²⁸ and this requires in-depth research such as the opinion Vieira ²⁹. Activities that aim to satisfy an individual's basic psychological needs (autonomy, competence and relatedness) make them more likely to feel that they are living a purposeful life ³⁰.

The practice of reasoning and making sense are two reasons to believe that the distinction is theoretically grounded if we want to improve our understanding of the concept of learning. We argue that well-designed physical education content and supervised pedagogical courses should be an essential part of preschool teacher education programs. This is because recognizing that effective content creation requires good knowledge of the content, students, and school contexts (Rink, 2014). During this course, prospective teachers should be given the opportunity to learn how to create instructional tasks that aim to produce quality physical education instruction at this grade level.

In doing so, we can be more confident that preschool teachers have the content and teaching practices necessary to provide children with better physical education learning experiences ³¹. When teachers have to make decisions about management or discipline, more experienced teachers tend to restate their expectations for students, vary the amount of praise or criticism they give students, find new ways to model appropriate behavior or performance, ask students to demonstrate their performance, ask more questions, and pay greater attention to individual ³².

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this study shows that the effectiveness of teaching Physical Education teachers in Medan still tends to focus on delivering information and applying basic skills, while further skill development and skill refinement receive less attention. This can hinder the optimal learning process for students. Therefore, a more balanced approach is needed in teaching, emphasizing gradual learning strategies, providing effective feedback, and developing students' skills progressively so that they not only understand basic movements, but are also able to hone and apply them better. There is no ideal process or progression for physical education learning. If there are no refinement, extension tasks, or too rapid transitions from information to application, the appropriateness of content development will be questioned.

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